

BORER'S PARADIGM IN THE CASE OF JAPANESE

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to apply the linguistic paradigm of Borer, who discusses, the problem of definiteness, on the case of Japanese Noun Phrases. It is well known that Japanese is an articleless language. As a matter of fact, we must endeavor to find novel manners through which definiteness is acquired in a language like Japanese, since we cannot rely on the existence of definite or indefinite articles like in English. For this reason, I chose to analyze the paradigm of Borer, who is the first author to create a comprehensible body of linguistic data in which she treated the problem of definiteness in a scientific manner, and this framework must be applied to Japanese Noun Phrases. It will help us prove that the different definiteness-bearers items in Japanese are not hazardous, but syntactically driven and they obtain definite interpretation for various NPs in Japanese.

Keywords: Classifiers, Japanese, Number, Plurality, Definiteness, Countability, Noun Phrases, Borer, Determiners

1. Borer's Paradigm on Definiteness applied to Japanese

There has been an assumption that definiteness is the study of noun phrases marked with definite and indefinite articles (Knimsky 1972; Christophersen 1939; Chesterman 1991). Because of such an assumption, which equates definiteness with the study of articles, definiteness in articleless languages like Japanese has been ignored until quite recently. However, there are some linguists, like DuBois (1980), who have recognized that the reference of definiteness should not be restricted to articles alone. He (1980: 204) argues that "*the range of contrasting reference items is much greater than the two article forms, and many crucial phenomena related to definiteness are either not found or not easily recognized*". Du Bois's view of definiteness opens up the possibility that there are other ways to express definiteness in languages. However, to unleash these possibilities of definiteness expressed in multiple manners, one must understand definiteness devoid of any bias. That is, even when it is accepted that articleless languages accept the interpretation of definiteness, the common approach to studying this phenomenon is to examine parallel translations of English and Japanese phrases with definite and indefinite articles, and to compare these in a satisfactory compilation (Kubo:1988 has a very interesting study related to this topic). This point of view is supported by the fact that anaphoricity plays an important role in English as well, with NPs being analyzed as definite through this phenomenon as Du Bois maintains in her paper (1980:131):

78. a. I got a table and an armchair delivered to my office.

b. They are already covered with books.

This is the most common employment of definite expressions which challenge the uniqueness based approaches and involves the intended referent of the definite to be introduced by a preceding indefinite. If it were for English to express definiteness through articles alone, Du Bois argues that such a mechanism should not have existed. She further maintains that the challenge for an uniqueness-based account of domain restriction is to formulate the general structure of such

restrictions so that the domain of indefinite and definite descriptions becomes syntactically driven at the deep level. In (1a) one may argue that the office itself becomes part of a definite Noun Phrase, at least semantically, since the noun is determined by a possessive pronoun and the universe of speech is completed with different sets of a sequence (furniture).

Most European languages like German, French or Romanian employ definite or indefinite articles to convey the notion of definite NPs. Definiteness is a multidimensional notion that can combine identification, specificity, referentiality, actualization, familiarity, individuation, genericity, and shared knowledge. Some combinations are (Kirtchuk, 2004:4)

2.

— definite referential, specific, identifying, cf. *The music* Γm listening pertains to Bach;

— indefinite referential, specific, nonidentifying, cf. *Air is a composition* Γm listening;

— definite referential, specific, shared knowledge, cf. I'm searching for *the answer* [I was searching] #

— indefinite referential, specific, nonshared knowledge cf. I'm searching for *an answer...* (≈ a moment before it existed) #

— referential, specific, cf. He's looking for *Tom Jones* (Inherently definite proper names)

— referential, specific, identifying: I'm searching for *the John* who was here two days ago

One of the major problems when translating from Japanese into an European language such as German or English is to determine definiteness of noun phrases in order to choose the correct determiner in the target language. Even though in Japanese, noun phrase reference is said to depend in large parts on the discourse context, we show that in many cases there also exist linguistic markers for definiteness. One interesting point to start with is the observation made by Tawa (2015) who claims that in Japanese there is an abundance of null-NPs and that anaphoricity is less likely to be employed syntactically than in English.

(3a) Did you read the novel;? (3b) Shosetsu_j o yomimashita ka?

a. Yes, I read it_j; yesterday. [_j letter-ACC wrote *Q'*

b. * Yes, I read [_i]; yesterday. 'Did [you]_i; read the novel_j ?'

(3c). ee kinou [L [_j] yomimashita.

Yes yesterday [] [] wrote

'Yes, [I]_i read [it]_j yesterday.'

What the sentences in (3) exhibits is the English full compound NP *the novel* in (3) is referred back through anaphor *it* in (3a) when the listener is believed to identify the referent of the pronoun in the opinion of the speaker. However, this compound noun phrase cannot be assimilated to a null-NP in English as shown in (3b). The sentences in (3c) are the Japanese equivalent of (3a). Contrary to the case of English, (3c) shows that it comes in handy to employ null-NPs for both the direct object and also for the subject in Japanese clauses when the listener is assumed to identify the referents of the null-NPs in the opinion of the speaker. Regarding the status of definiteness of null-NPs in Japanese, Kubo (1988) had already claimed that null-NPs are inherently definite. She introduces the following instance to prove her point (Kubo 1992:78-79):

(4) a. Watashi-wa honya de torusutoi no hon o katta. *Pron.I, TOP., N.Bookstore, PREP., N.Tolstoy, GEN, N.Book-ACC, Pred:Past.Buy* 'I bought a book_i by Tolstoy.'

b. Shikashi watashi-ga [_j] yomu mae-ni ootoo-ga [_i] yabutte shimatta. . *Conj.But, Pron.I-NOM []_i, Pred.Read before-OAT brother-NOM []_j, Pred:PAST.Tear* 'But before I read it_i; my brother tore [up] the book_j.'

According to her, the vast majority of nouns are inherently definite null-NPs in Japanese, because there is an evident relation of anaphoricity where the null-NPs in (81) goes back to the previously depicted NP *hon* 'book' in (81a). Kubo (1988) has made an important contribution to the field of Japanese linguistics, since her study is the first attempt to investigate the realization of definiteness in Japanese by showing that there is a coherent system for the interpretation of the definite status. She (1988:22-23) discusses the notion of definiteness based on the following definition: "*a definite NP refers to an entity that is in some sense given in the conversational common ground, whereas an indefinite NP refers to an entity that is newly added to the conversational domain*". Based on this definition, she explains what definite NPs are. She (1988:28) says that she uses "*the term definite for NPs which are either anaphoric or generic on the basis of the traditional notion of definiteness*". Kubo uses the term anaphoric in Kuno's (1973:39) sense, which says that an anaphoric noun phrase "*has some specific referent in the universe of discourse, but [it] also has already been referred to, so that listeners know what the speaker is*

talking about" Our approach proposes that classifiers are the main means of expressing definiteness in Japanese, an articleless language like Vietnamese or Chinese. This follows from a set of properties that characterizes both Numerals and Classifiers in Japanese:

a. The employment of numerals alone cannot express countability independently, but it depends on the syntactic relation to a highly specified classifier which, together with the numeral, form a Nominal Phrase, meaning that it behaves like a nominal adjective:

(5) ichi-*(rin)-no- hana
Num.One, CLASS, GEN., N.Flower „One Flower”

b. Nouns are not marked for plurality whatsoever, with a few exceptions like *-tachi*, or *-gata*, which act like suffixes and are lexical in nature (the same noun as (5) is used in the following examples below). Moreover, kinds can be denoted by bare nouns (Krifka 1995): .

(6) go-rin-no hana (7) takusan-no hana
Num.Five, CLASS., GEN, N.Flower Adv.Many, GEN., N.Flower ‘Five flowers’ ‘A lot of flowers’

Direct modification by numerals is incompatible in determining nouns for mandatory classifier languages, and, as a consequence, they don't allow counting. For this reason, classifiers are employed to turn Number devoid Japanese nouns into countable NPs. Classifiers become an inherent part of a NP and they adjoin most numerals (Shibatani, 2004:202). From this definition it comes that definiteness must be a direct corollary of the structure of Number in classifier languages like Japanese or Chinese. Naturally, they function as a means of individuation and render definite expressions *per-se*. Countable classifiers cannot be used with uncountable nouns since the latter are expressed by plain numerals:

(7)

a. Koerisan wa chizu o *ikko* katta. *N. Tanaka, COP., N.Bread, ACC., Num.One, CLASS., V.PAST.Buy* Koeri acquired one cheese. (a whole load)

b. Koerisan wa chizu o *sankin* katta. *N. Tanaka, COP., N.Bread, ACC., N.Three, CLASS., V.PAST.Buy* Koeri acquired three pieces of cheese. Japanese marks the distinction between integral and divided mass nouns through classifiers as well, something that English does not. Example 85(a) makes use of a generic classifier while example 85(b) proposes a highly specified classifier, in which the noun becomes definite. My thesis intends to demonstrate that there are several other methods of expressing definiteness in Japanese, apart from the usage of classifiers, a subject that has been debated by many linguists. Indeed, nominalizations or the employment of arguments in Japanese can also bear definite interpretation on the NP they determine. This can be easily demonstrated by bringing into discussion the similitude between classifiers and nominalized constructions or arguments, since they both involve two or more elements to form the NP. Moreover, unlike English, where the grammatical value of a lexeme is changed grammatically, in Japanese, more often than not, we encounter the particle „NO” which transforms, for

example, a verb into a noun without the need for suffixes, as in other European languages. The most appropriate examples are those including two particles and the conversion of adjectives or verbs into nouns:

8 a. [Ano chiisai-*no-o*] mottekudasai.
(*modified* *nominal*)

Dem.That,Adj.Big,PART.Nom.,PART.Acc.,V.IMP.Give
.,Pol.Suff. 'Please bring me the small one.'

b. [John-ga tsukutta *no o*] miseteagemasu.
(*headless* *relative*)

PronPers.You,PART.Nom.,V.PAST.Make,PART.Gen.,
PART.Acc,V.IMP.show 'Show me what John made.'

c. [Hanako-wa sakana-o yai-ta-*no-o*] tabe-ta.
(*head-internal* *relative*) *N.*

Hanako, TOP., N.Fish, PART.Acc., V.PAST.Broil, PART.
Gen., PART.Acc, V.PAST.Eat 'Hanako ate the fish that she cooked.'

Yamada (1985:42) states that Japanese NPs as group elements have the following functions: complements of a preposition (9), modifiers of a noun (10), complements of a noun (11) and there is almost always involved a particle. While arguing in favor of his thesis, Mutsune (1993:11) says that such observations are limited to the paradigm presented by English and also proposes that NPs as group elements can have the function of adjuncts (12), suggesting they act as definite markers:

9. Kare wa saikō no senshu ni takai daishō o haratta. *Pron.He, PART.Nom., N.Excellence, PART.Gen., N.Player, PART.Dat., Adj.High, N.Price, PART.Acc. V.Pay* He paid a high price *for the best player.*

10. Saiyūshū senshu no topikku wa kaigi de happyō saremasendeshita. *N.Excellence, N.Player PART.Nom. N.Topic PART.Nom. N.Conference PART.Acc. V.Present* The topic regarding the best player was not presented at the meeting.

11. Gorufā no Jon Minsuku wa kōkyū o kaseide imasu. *N.Golf PART.Gen, N.John Minsk, PART.Nom., N.high salary, PART.Acc. V.earn* John Minsk, the golf player, earns a high salary.

12. Tsuki to hoshi ga deau toki, koibito-tachi wa kisuwoshita. *N.Moon,Conj.,N.Star, PART.Nom.,V.Meet,Prep.,N.Lover,PART.Nom.,V.Past.Kiss* The lovers kissed when the moon meets the stars.

3.2.Conclusions of This Section

We have seen in the previous chapter that a semantic approach towards definiteness in Japanese poses serious threats to our thesis, since various interpretations of the semantic content of the nouns can lead to either the definite or indefinite status of a noun in Japanese, and that status is highly dependent on contextual references in the form of anaphoric or cataphoric criteria. For example, Horiguchi (1995) states that nouns counting as <Unspecified Part>.in a

sentence are indefinite, while Niwa (2013) claims these can sometimes be analyzed as topics of existence and are definite in nature. Such contradictions are eloquent in the sense one should follow another path and try to demonstrate that definiteness in Japanese holds syntactic grounds as a genuine linguistic phenomenon never prone to divergent opinions. Our first attempt was to show that some authors like Kubo (1988) and Tawa (2015) endeavor to explain the lack of Gender and Number in Japanese by suggesting that Japanese nouns are inherently definite and the rationale emerges from the abundance of null-NPs which behave specifically in that they do not usually employ anaphoricity so often than in English, because anaphoricity is intrinsically implicated in the structure of Japanese nouns. With this in mind, the semantic approach presented previously sounds redundant, but the efforts are still yet fruitless, as a result of the fact that we did not find any novel method by means of which the lack of articles in Japanese is overcome. One first attempt was to show there is a slightly different meaning when counting nouns, since the employment of classifiers in 85(b) plays the same role as in English, namely to differentiate collective or mass notions, unlike 85(a) where the numeral is singularly used to instantiate the number of items available from a certain string of lexemes. For this fact, one can assume classifiers act as bearers of definite interpretation for the noun they determine. Another goal of my thesis is to demonstrate that there are several other methods of expressing definiteness in Japanese, apart from the usage of classifiers, a subject that has been debated by many linguists. One process which sparked my attention is the behavior of nominalizations or the employment of arguments in Japanese, since they exhibit a heterogenous specificity that cannot be found in European languages and consists primarily of the Genitive particle "no". The assumption that nominalizations in Japanese are also bearers of definite interpretation issues from the similitude between classifiers and nominalized constructions or arguments, since they both involve two or more elements to form the Noun Phrase.

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